

PRINCIPALS' INTERPERSONAL RELATIONSHIP AND ORGANIZATIONAL JUSTICE AS PREDICTORS OF VICE PRINCIPALS' WORK BEHAVIOURS IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ANAMBRA STATE, NIGERIA, WEST AFRICA

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated principals' interpersonal relationship and organizational justice as predictors of vice principals' work behaviours in secondary schools in Anambra State. It investigated respect for diversity and procedural justice as two dimensions of principals' behaviours that can impact vice principals' work behaviours. The population of the study was 532 vice principals, made up of 266 Vice Principals Administration (VP Admins) and 266 Vice Principals Academics (VP Acads) in the 266 public secondary schools in the six education zones of the state. The sample of the study was all the 532 vice principals. The entire population was studied. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. The correlational research design was employed in the study. Three instruments, namely, "Principals' Interpersonal Relationship Scale for Vice Principals (PIRSVP), Principals' Organizational Justice Scale for Vice Principals (POJSVP) and Vice Principals' Work Behaviours Scale (VPWBS) were used to collect data. PIRSVP and POJSVP were adapted, while VPWBS was constructed by the researchers. The internal reliability consistency of the instruments was established after administering them on 20 vice principals in 20 public secondary schools in Enugu State and using the Cronbach reliability test analysis. An average reliability coefficient of 0.86 was obtained from the three instruments. 532 questionnaires were administered by the researchers with the help of six research assistants. 521 out of the 532 questionnaires were completely filled by the respondents and retrieved by the instrument administrators. The simple regression analysis was used. The findings of the study showed that respect for diversity and procedural justice had moderate predictive values on vice principals work behaviours. These predictive values were also found to be significant to vice principals' work behaviours. It was recommended that principals should have high regard for vice principals and treat them with equity and fairness. It was also recommended that vice principals and other school members should respect principals too.

Keywords: Principals, Interpersonal Relationship, Organizational Justice, Vice Principals, Work Behaviours

Introduction

In Nigeria, public secondary school principals are head teachers appointed by the government to oversee the smooth running of the schools. Secondary school principals are therefore pivotal to the achievement of the educational goals of the secondary schools. This is because every aspect of the school operation revolves around them. Principals' leadership position is so important that the Wallace Foundation (2023) described it as the most pressing matter of public education, behind quality teachers. People for Education (2021) confirmed that principals make the most significant impact on students' learning and on the teaching process. Principals perform diverse and complex roles, all of which are essential to the achievement of the secondary school goals. Robbin (2021) referred to principals as leaders, administrators, advocates, representatives. They are teachers, guardians, implementers of government and education ministry visions and policies, managers of resources and people, relationship facilitators. In fact, the list of roles performed by principals in the secondary schools seems to be endless. For principals to effectively coordinate all these roles for the schools to succeed, the appointment of vice principals emerged as these roles are too many for a single individual.

Vice principals are one of the core components of the school organization and its productivity and efficiency. Vice principals are teachers appointed by the government to be responsible for assisting the principals in the organization, administration and supervision of the secondary schools. Van Niekerk (2022) opined that the appointment of vice principals is to assist principals in the administration of the schools. Thus, the appointment of vice principals all over the world, particularly in Anambra State, is to lessen principals' heavy administrative and instructional roles and thus, assist principals to achieve the goals of that level of education. Vice principals' importance in the secondary schools was substantiated by Ho, Kang and Shaari (2020) when they referred to vice principals as boundary spanners. They perform multiple and complex roles in the secondary schools. In fact, there is not much difference between the roles of principals and vice principals. In spite of these overlapping roles of principals and vice principals, Baker (2023) and Swain (2021) clarified that the role of vice principals remains contingent on the direction and delegation from principals. This implies that vice principals can only act when and as directed by principals. Based on this relationship, Van Niekerk (2022) advised principals and vice principals to work in complementary partnership to advance students' academic and social learning. For vice principals, particularly in Anambra State to work effectively in this complementary partnership with principals, principals ought to establish a positive, working interpersonal relationship with vice principals, reinforced by their organizational justice.

Interpersonal relationship within an organization is the relationship between one individual employee and another, between one individual employee and a group and between a group and another group within and beyond the work environment. Nwinyiokpugi and Omunakwe (2019) defined interpersonal relationship as the day to day interaction between leaders and employees in an organization. It is the relationship between two or more persons who interact and fulfill one or more physical and social needs with shared identical goals and interest (Oguzie, Obi and Chigbu 2020). Thus, the building of a positive and constructive working relationship between principals and vice principals is crucial when considering the fact that their roles and relationship are intimately connected (Swain, 2021) and are all meant for the achievement of the shared goals and interest of the secondary schools. Principals' interpersonal relationship with vice principals in this work is therefore, the friendly and considerate way principals treat vice principals as their immediate ranking subordinates in secondary schools in Anambra State.

In every organization, the quality of interpersonal relationship, especially of leaders determines the behaviours of employees both at work and in their private lives. Szostek (2019) opined that a high quality interpersonal relationship has many positive behavioural outcomes, such as commitment, performance, motivation, innovation, error detection, team work, external and internal organizational communication. Conversely, low quality interpersonal relationships have negative impacts on these aspects of an organization's operation (Szostek, 2019). In the secondary schools, principals' good interpersonal relationship has been associated with such behavioural outcomes as teachers' commitment, job satisfaction, engagement (Thompson and Unachukwu, 2020), participation and organizational citizenship behaviours (Annisa, 2023), students' academic, social learning and lifelong achievements (Koula, 2015). Conversely, principals' negative interpersonal relationship has been associated with staff absence of trust (Havold and Havold, 2019), interpersonal rejection (Leary, 2015), frustration, absenteeism, turnover (Van Vulpen, 2023), poor students' academic performance and dropout rates (Conradson, 2019). Principals' interpersonal relationship can therefore cause vice principals to exhibit negative work behaviours. Principals' interpersonal relationship with vice principals and other school members include respecting the differences in the members, caring about their wellbeing both within and outside the schools, communicating in a timely and dignified manner to them, bearing with their weaknesses, valuing their contributions to the school.

Organizational justice is another behaviour of principals which affect vice principals' and other school members' behaviours. Organizational justice is the feeling of not being cheated or neglected as perceived by subordinates in a work environment. Lombardo (2021) defined organizational justice as employees' perception of fairness within an organization. Conrad (2021) viewed principals' organizational justice as the employees' perception of the school principals' behaviours, decisions and actions and how they impact the employees' attitudes and behaviours. Principals' organizational justice in the context of this work is vice principals' feeling that principals relate well with them and treat them well in their complementary partnership with principals in Anambra State secondary schools.

Organizational justice practised by principals in secondary schools is the strongest determinant of the entire staff work engagement, commitment, performance and school goal attainment. Resti and Mangundjaya (2016), Tan (2014), Nwinyokpugi and Omunakwe (2019) confirmed that employees' strong perception of organizational justice makes them to display positive behaviours, while negative perception of it makes them to exhibit negative behaviours. Organizational justice has been associated with many organizational behavioural outcomes, such as increased job satisfaction, innovative work behaviours, organizational citizenship behaviours, organizational commitment, work performance and engagement (Srimulyani and Hermanto, 2022). Contrarily, organizational injustice has been associated with employees' apathy, disengagement, organizational silence, reduction in other positive behaviours, and consequently, reduced output of employees (Tan, 2014). Principals' organizational justice can therefore cause vice principals to behave in a friendly or unfriendly way towards the principals and other school members as well as towards their job responsibilities in the school.

Principals' organizational justice includes the equitable way principals share the human and material resources available in the school (Adelotan, 2021). It also includes recognizing, respecting, appreciating, valuing, delegating duties and rewarding school staff by merit (Halliday, 2021), ensuring workers' professional development, involving staff in decision makings that affect the school (Ofojebe and Akudo, 2021), sympathizing and empathizing with staff in times of difficulty, sharing in the staff's joyful moments, among other things.

This implies that if principals in Anambra State apply the positive organizational justice and avoid the negative ones, vice principals and other staff in the school will work with committed spirit to achieve the goals of the schools. This suggests that when principals treat vice principals fairly and equitably, vice principals behave and work better.

There are different dimensions of interpersonal relationship and organizational justice. The National School Climate Centre (NSCC, 2012) recognized three components of interpersonal relationship principals ought to exhibit within the school organization. These are: respect for diversity, school connectedness and community partnership (social support). Similarly, Bhabiri (2021) and Obalade and Mtembu (2023) in their works identified three dimensions of organizational justice namely, distributive justice, procedural justice and interactional justice.

Respect for diversity is the way organizational leaders respect each individual worker's differences without any discrimination. School connectedness is viewed by the NSCC as students' feeling that their teachers and peers love and care for them and their wellbeing at school. Community partnership is an aspect of principals' interpersonal relationship which makes him to effectively coordinate students' families and other stakeholders of the school community in a collaborative and interdependent relationship for the smooth and successful running of the schools. Distributive justice is the way employees perceive organizational leaders' distribution of the resources of the organization as fair or unfair. Procedural justice is employees' perception of how organizational leaders have objectively and impartially implemented the elements and outcomes of the organization by following established norms, laws, rules and regulations and other organizational standards in their decision makings. Interactional justice is the respectful, caring, sensitive and considerate way organizational leaders treat employees. In this study, respect for diversity and procedural justice as aspects of principals' interpersonal relationship and organizational justice which could predict vice principals' work behaviours were investigated.

Respect for diversity is one of the components of interpersonal relationship of school principals which affect both students' and workers' behaviours in the school. Respect for diversity is viewed by the NSCC as principals' treating everyone equally and fairly, regardless of their race, gender, age, religion, socio-economic status. It is principals' creation of an inclusive, caring and supporting school community that engages members in a respectful, empathetic manner (The Eastern Michigan University, 2023), by acting with respect, sensitivity and tolerance of individuals of the school members with many differences, such as gender, language, religion, race, ethnicity, origin, personality, political view, by accepting them as they are (Polat, Arslan and Ölgüm, 2017). Polat et al., affirmed that principals' ability to effectively manage individual and socio-cultural differences facilitate organizational goal achievement while inability to do so results to social divisions and conflicts and negative work behaviour outcomes. This implies that vice principals work better when principals accept them as they are, without any discrimination.

Procedural justice is an aspect of principals' organizational justice that enhances workers' work behaviours. Procedural justice is the perception of an employee that the organization he or she works in, adopts fair policies, laws, rules, regulations and other organizational standards that allow him or her to voice out in the decision making processes of the organization. In this type of justice, equality, consistency, accuracy, non-biased decisions are important factors that determine workers' perception of fair treatment by managers. Thompson and Unachukwu (2020) opined that employees' sense of fair treatment is positive when organizational leaders apply an objective approach to the decision-making and implementation of procedural justice. Tyokusu, Emakwu and Ejoha (2019) buttressed that the equality of the decision-making process is more important to the employee than amount of

rewards received, as far as the processes are consistent, non-biased, accurate and correct, allows for appeals and grievances and represents the individual and organizational work elements. When leaders employ objectivity and impartiality in their approaches, the individuals' feeling or perception of fair treatment is enhanced. When they are biased or impartial in the implementation of policies, laws, and other organizational established standards, they evoke feelings of dissatisfaction in the workers. This feeling can also affect the staff's work behaviours negatively. This implies that when principals in Anambra State secondary schools support and care for vice principals, when they give vice principals a voice in the decision making processes of the school, when they are neutral and transparent in the way they handle issues between vice principals and other school members, it enhances vice principals' feeling of procedural justice and boosts their work behaviours.

Work behaviours are those behaviours exhibited by employees in the workplace which can promote, lessen, hinder or even ruin the attainment of organizational goals. Keka Resource (2023) defined work behaviours as a person's intent or way of communicating with other people at the workplace. In other words, it is employees' reactions to a particular situation at the workplace (Keka Resource, 2023). Vice principals' work behaviours in the context of this work, are those things vice principals do which either facilitate or hinder the progress of the school goal achievement. Work behaviours can be negative or positive, explicit or implicit, verbal or non-verbal, physical or emotional. They include rudeness, gossip, bullying (Ali, 2023), prejudices, stereotyping, discrimination (Fansworth, Clark, Green, Lopez, Wysocki and Kepner, 2020), smiling, frowning, aggression, physical fights, angry words, silence, defiance, connivance, indifference, job commitment, job performance, altruism, job engagement.

Work behaviours are the most critical area for human resource professions to work on (Keka Resource, 2023). This is because the behaviours of people determines the organization's success and efficiency (Rabha, 2022). Employees' work behaviours have been positively linked to high morale, collaboration, cohesiveness, job performance, engagement, retention and productivity (Ali, 2023). It is negatively related to decreased morale, performance, distraction, conflicts, harassment, damage to organizational reputation, decreased output, job loss, absenteeism, turnover (Picincu, 2020). This implies that vice principals' work behaviours can negatively or positively affect the relationship of principals and other school members, thus marring the attainment of the secondary school goals. It suggests that principals in Anambra State should improve their interpersonal relationship with vice principals and ensure that they treat vice principals with fairness and equity (organizational justice) so as to enhance and sustain their positive work behaviours.

The many different types of work behaviours exhibited by employees in every organization have been subsumed by scholars, such as Greenberg (2012), Lor (2019), Majumber (2024) and research organizations (Saylor Academy, 2024, Human Resource Business Partner, 2024) into four major types. These are: job performance, organizational citizenship, absenteeism and turnover. These work behaviours strongly affect educational achievement. The choice of these four work behaviours was premised on the great paucity of research works on vice principals, especially on vice principals' work behaviours in relation to principals' interpersonal relationship and organizational justice in Nigeria, particularly, in Anambra State.

Job performance level of organizational staff is strongly determined by their perception of interpersonal relationship and organizational justice of the leaders and the organization (University of Minnesota, 2023). Ihueze, Unachukwu and Onyali (2018) agreed that staff motivation through principals' good interpersonal relationship and organizational justice

results to staff job satisfaction, commitment, high performance and students' overall achievement. Contrarily, destructive relationship and organizational injustice create friction and unhealthy rivalry and dampen the performance of employees (Lewis, Olowo and Okotoni, 2022). Similarly, absenteeism is very detrimental to school goal achievement, Absenteeism transcends mere physical absence of an employee from work during scheduled work hours. Absenteeism includes arriving late to work, skipping work days, spending more time on personal matters than the organization's (Van Vulpen, 2023). It also includes extending tea break time, attending to personal issues like business, faking illness, attending to sick family members (Nombo, Nyangarika and Mwesiga, 2020), lack of punctuality, observance of minimum hours of work (Hawks, 2023), leaving before the work hours' elapse and withdrawal behaviours (showing indifference or aloofness to the organization's activities even while physically present). Thus, any day vice principals or any other staff absent themselves from school, has negative impact on students' and staff's outcomes, such as academic performance and dropout rates (Conradson, 2021). It also has negative impact on staff (including principals') workload, students' and staff mental health (Gallen-Tessonneau, Johnson and Keppens, 2019). It causes conflicts, job dissatisfaction, poor job performance (Ofojebe and Akudo, 2021) and delay in achieving school objectives and programmes, such as examinations, graduation, staff evaluation and promotion within a specified time frame.

Organizational citizenship in schools or any other organization is also associated with the leaders' interpersonal relationship and organizational justice. It is an employee who shares friendly relationship with the leader (and colleagues) based on fair and just treatment that can develop a strong psychological association with the organization. Keka Resource (2023) affirmed that interpersonal relationship with managers and leaders foster a safe and positive work environment where employees feel empowered to volunteer solutions and help those around them. Nesiayali (2018) reiterated that employees volunteer for tasks that are not part of their job responsibilities whenever they develop a strong association with the organization. Equally, staff turnover is associated with leaders' interpersonal relationship and organizational justice. Jun, Hu and Sun (2023), Filippidis (2024) and Thompson (2023) affirmed that poor relationships with managers are the real cause of employees leaving their organizations. Halliday (2021) confirmed that one of the reasons employees leave their job, is to escape ineffective and toxic managers. In other words, when a manager is unfair or unfriendly, an employee will always feel like quitting the job (Ugoani, 2018). This implies that principals in Anambra State have to relate well with vice principals and ensure the application of positive organizational justice so as to enhance vice principals' commitment to their responsibilities towards goal achievement in the schools.

In every work environment, it is expected that the leaders or employers would treat all their employees equally and fairly, irrespective of their ethnic, cultural or religious affiliations. Unfortunately, the reverse is the case in Anambra State (Thompson and Unachukwu, 2020). Ihueze, Unachukwu and Onyali (2018) noted principals' discrimination, favouritism and prejudice in the performance appraisal and rewarding of staff which affects staff job performance. There is a hostile, dishonest and unfriendly attitude towards the staff (Oshia, Chukwudi and Obionu, 2022), lack of interest in the welfare and professional development of staff (Akudo and Ibeh, 2021), inability to arrest loitering behaviours, make out time to visit staff and communicate with them (Emengini, Sam-Omenyi and Nwankwo, 2022), inability to involve staff in decision makings (Okeke, Okaforcha and Ekwesianya, 2021). Many principals assign heavy workloads to some staff without other benefits (Okeke, Okaforcha and Ezinine, 2021). These behaviours of principals have led to such negative behaviours of staff as non-commitment to duty, lack of interest, low morale and job dissatisfaction (Emengini, Sam-Omenyi and Nwankwo, 2022), strained relationships between principals and

staff (Thompson and Ofojebe, 2020), staff failure to perform additional roles (Oshia, Chukwudi and Obionu, 2022) and massive withdrawal of staff from the schools (Thompson and Unachukwu, 2020).

The researchers also noticed that some principals in contempt of, or indifference to the vice principals, relate information to vice principals by proxy, even when the vice principals are available. For instance, instead of directly talking to vice principals, they pass information to the vice principals through a teacher, a non-teaching staff or even a menial job worker in the school, such as a cook or sweeper. They delegate some teachers and even non-academic staff to do jobs that are vice principals' statutory job specifications, without any explanation to vice principals for such delegation. Some of the principals exclude the vice principals in the decision making processes of the school. Principals' behaviours like these show that such principals do not relate well with the vice principals. Such behaviours confirm Navarro-Corona and Slater (2019)'s observation that principals and vice principals do not form work teams and show little concern for participation with one another. They also corroborate Aja-Okorie and Oko (2021), Ruto (2011), Suleiman (2023) and Undiyaunde and Basake (2020)'s observations that lack, inappropriate/poor delegation of staff duties by principals, creates apathy in the secondary schools, especially in Nigeria and particularly in Anambra State.

When principals relate well with vice principals and other school members, it boosts their work behaviours. Swain (2021) emphasized that a mentor-leader approach of interpersonal relationship should be adopted by principals towards vice principals, rather than a leader-subordinate approach. This he maintained, would provide vice principals with partnership based on trust, loyalty and critically honours the autonomy and agency of the vice principals in the fulfilment of their leadership tasks. Principals must therefore provide vice principals with a good work environment through a cordial, friendly and considerate interpersonal relationship and organizational justice so that vice principals can collaborate effectively with principals in their complementary partnership roles through their positive work behaviours.

Vice principals' work behaviours in the secondary schools seem to vary according to the interpersonal relationship and organizational justice they experience from the principals. In Anambra State, the researchers' personal observation and interaction with some vice principals in some secondary schools showed that some of them work happily, enthusiastically and energetically in the schools. Some sacrifice their time and even life for the good of the schools. Meanwhile, some of them appear neglected by the principals and thus, show cold attitude, aloofness, aggression and indifference towards the schools' activities. The researchers also noticed that in the absence of the principals, some of these vice principals refuse to act for the principals. Instead, they refer such matters which their statutory position obligates them, to the principals' typists or secretaries who relay such information to the principals. They grudge and make sarcastic remarks about the principals. Behaviours like these are indications that such vice principals are not in good terms with the principals. This therefore necessitated the researchers' investigation of principals' interpersonal relationship and organizational justice as predictors of vice principals' work behaviours in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Statement of the Problem

Vice principals are neglected entities in the secondary schools and in research studies. Myriads of research studies in the secondary education system show evidence of this neglect as they focus majorly on principals, teachers and students. Thus, there is a dearth of research works that investigated vice principals as important components of the school system. One of the main factors that make vice principals neglected entities in the schools, is their

interpersonal relationship with principals and the type of organizational justice practised by the principals. When principals value, respect, love, honour, support and care for vice principals, when they treat vice principals with equity and fairness, it makes other school members to recognize and value vice principals. When vice principals are disregarded by the principals, it belittles vice principals' image, demoralizes vice principals and causes them to exhibit negative work behaviours. One of the researchers was a vice principal for several years and experienced principals' interpersonal relationship and organizational justice in their negative and positive forms. This actually affected her work behaviours in the school and her entire life, thus she and her research colleague considered this aspects of principals' leadership behaviours worth bringing to the limelight.

In Anambra State, principals' interpersonal relationship and organizational justice have been identified as two of the major problems bedeviling principals' relationship with school staff. But there is a great paucity of research studies that have investigated the interpersonal relationship between principals and vice principals as two prominent leaders of the schools, the type of organizational justice principals adopts towards vice principals and how they affect vice principals' work behaviours. No study has been specifically carried out in Anambra State on principals' respect for diversity and procedural justice as predictors of vice principals' work behaviours in secondary schools in Anambra State. This was the motivating factor behind this research study. The study investigated principals' respect for diversity and procedural justice as predictors of vice principals' job performance, organizational citizenship, absenteeism and turnover in secondary schools in Anambra State. The problem of the study put into question is, "What is the value of prediction that exists between principals' interpersonal relationship and organizational justice and vice principals' work behaviours in secondary schools in Anambra State?"

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to determine principals' interpersonal relationship and organizational justice as predictors of vice principals' work behaviours in secondary school in Anambra State. The study sought to determine principals'

1. respect for diversity as a predictor of vice principals' work behaviours in secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. procedural justice as a predictor of vice principals' work behaviours in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Questions

Two research questions were asked as follows:

1. What is the predictive value of principals' respect for diversity on vice principals' work behaviours in secondary schools in Anambra State?
2. What is the predictive value of procedural justice on vice principals' work behaviours in secondary schools in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

Two null hypotheses were postulated as follows:

1. Principals' respect for diversity will not significantly predict vice principals' work behaviours in secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Principals' procedural justice will not significantly predict vice principals' work behaviours in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Method

It was a correlational research study that involved 532 participants, made up of 266 Vice Principals Administration and 266 Vice Principals Academics (known as VP Admins and VP Acads in Nigerian informal parlance) in the 266 public secondary schools in Anambra State. The sample was the 532 participants. The entire population was sampled. Three instruments, namely, Principals' Interpersonal Relationship and Organizational Justice Scale for Vice Principals (PIRSVP), Principals Organizational Justice Scale for Vice Principals (POJSVP) and Vice Principals' Work Behaviours Scale (VPWBS) were used to collect data. PIRSVP was adapted from the Interpersonal Relationship Scale of the National School Climate Centre's Comprehensive School Climate Inventory and modified by the researcher to suit the context of the study. POJSVP was adapted from Colquitt (2001)'s Organizational Justice Scale modified by Omar, Salessib, Vaamonde and Urteaga (2017), while Vice Principals' Work Behaviours Scale (VPWBS) was constructed by the researchers. PIRSVP measured respect for diversity while POJSVP measured procedural justice as aspects of principals' relationship that affect vice principals' work behaviours. VPWBS measured four vice principals' work behaviours, namely, job performance, organizational citizenship, absenteeism and turnover. The three instruments were submitted for face validation to three research experts in the Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka. The reliability of the instruments was established by administering them on 20 vice principals administration and vice principals academics in 20 public secondary schools in Enugu State. The Cronbach alpha reliability test was used for the computation of the internal consistency of the three instruments. The internal reliability consistency of the instruments yielded an average reliability coefficient of 0.86

The researchers involved six research assistants from the six education zones who helped them to get to the target population. One of the research assistants is a personnel of the Nigerian Civil Defence and Service Corps (NCDSC) whose duty post takes her to the riverine areas of Anambra State. The other five research assistants were teachers in the different education zones. The researchers and the research assistants went directly to the schools to solicit for the participants' response to the questionnaires. The researchers and their assistants solicited for on-the-spot response from the participants. Any participants who could not respond on the spot was asked to tell the instrument administrators when they would possibly come to collect the instruments administered. Out of the 532 questionnaires administered, 521 were completely filled and returned, giving a 98% return rate. This percentage was used for data analysis. The data were analyzed using simple regression analysis. Muijs' (2004) cited in Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2007) suggestion for assessing the goodness of fit of regression model using squared regression coefficient (R^2) was adopted for the research questions. Where: 0 - 0.1 = weak, 0.2- 0.3=modest, 0.4 - 0.5 = moderate, > 0.5 = strong prediction. For the null hypotheses, p-value was used to determine the significance of the prediction. Where the calculated p-value was less than the stipulated level of significance (0.05), the null hypothesis was rejected. Whereas the null hypothesis was not rejected where the calculated p-value was greater than the stipulated level of significance (0.05).

Results

Research Question 1: What is the predictive value of principals' respect for diversity on vice principals' work behaviours in secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 1. Summary of Simple Regression Analysis of Principals' Respect for Diversity as a Predictor of Vice Principals' Work Behaviours in secondary schools in Anambra State

	R	R ²	Adj.R ²	B	SE B	B
Constant				6.83	1.52	
Respect for Diversity	.73	.54	.54	1.40	.05	.73

The summary of the simple regression analysis as shown in the above table indicates that principals' respect for diversity is a strong predictor of vice principals' work behaviours in secondary schools in Anambra State. This is shown by the regression coefficient ($R = .73$) and the coefficient of determination ($R^2 = .54$) which indicates that principals' respect for diversity explained 54% of the variance in vice principals' work behaviours.

Research Question 2: What is the predictive value of principals' procedural justice on vice principals' work behaviours in secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 2. Summary of Simple Regression Analysis of Principals' Procedural Justice as a Predictor of Vice Principals' Work Behaviours in secondary schools in Anambra State

	R	R ²	Adj.R ²	B	SE B	B
Constant				17.03	1.26	
Procedural Justice	.69	.48	.48	1.88	.08	.69

Data in Table 2 indicates that principals' procedural justice is a moderate predictor of vice principals work behaviours in secondary schools in Anambra State. This is shown by the regression coefficient ($R = .69$) and the coefficient of determination ($R^2 = .48$).

Hypothesis 1: Principals' respect for diversity will not significantly predict vice principals' work behaviours in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 3: Significance of Simple Regression Analysis of Principals' Respect for Diversity as a Predictor of Vice Principals' Work Behaviours in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Predictor	R	R ²	F(1,524)	p-value	Decision
Respect for Diversity	.73	.54	631.24	.000	Significant

The simple regression result displayed in Table 3 shows that principals' respect for diversity is a significant predictor of vice principals' work behaviours in secondary schools in Anambra State, $R = .73$, $F(1,524) = 631.24$ and p -value < 0.05 . Since the obtained p -value was less than stipulated 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Hypothesis 2: Principals’ procedural justice will not significantly predict vice principals’ work behaviours in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 4: Significance of Simple Regression Analysis of Principals’ Procedural Justice as a Predictor of Vice Principals’ Work Behaviours in secondary schools in Anambra State

Predictor	R	R ²	F(1,542)	p-value	Decision
Procedural Justice	.69	.48	493.48	.000	Significant

Table 4 shows that principals’ procedural justice is a significant predictor of vice principals’ work behaviours in secondary schools in Anambra State., $R = .69$, $F(1,542) = 493.48$ and p -value < 0.05 . Since the obtained p -value was less than stipulated 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Discussions

Table 1 shows that respect for diversity is a moderate predictor of vice principals’ work behaviours. Any variable which has a moderate prediction on another variable establishes a significance to the variable and this is evidenced in Table 3. This shows that respect for diversity is significant to vice principals’ work behaviours. It shows that respect for diversity is crucial in the effective operation of secondary schools and the achievement of its goals through vice principals’ positive work behaviours. When principals respect vice principals, irrespective of their socio-economic or cultural backgrounds, it makes vice principals to behave well in the discharge of their duties. This finding corroborates Gavino, Lambert and Akinlade (2021), Valento, Lourento and Neineth (2023) whose research studies associated respect for diversity with school outcomes, such as job satisfaction, organizational citizenship, absenteeism, turnover, engagement. It also agrees with Polat, Arslam and Ölgüm (2017)’s assertion that principals’ ability to manage individual and socio-cultural differences is a factor that facilitates schools’ efficiency and goal attainment. This finding agrees with the researchers’ opinion that vice principals in secondary schools in Anambra State would behave and work well if principals loved, supported, cared about them and accepted them as they are, without any discrimination.

In table 2, the result of the study shows procedural justice as a moderate predictor of vice principals’ work behaviours. This prediction is significant as shown in Table 4. It means that procedural justice is vital to school members’ participation in the school goal achievement. When principals consistently and firmly implement procedural justice between vice principals and other school members, it boosts vice principals’ feeling of fair treatment and commitment to the schools. The finding however, disagrees with Srivasta (2015) who found out that procedural justice had no significant prediction on organizational commitment. The disparity in the two studies could be as a result of the difference in the population and location. While Srivasta carried out her study on health personnel in India, this study was carried out in the education system and on principals and vice principals. However, the result agrees with Castillo and Fernandez (2017) who found a relationship between procedural justice and students’ satisfaction. It also agrees with Moon and McCluskey (2023)’s finding that school leaders’ inconsistency in the implementation of procedural justice in handling issues or cases of victimized teachers is responsible for their negative emotional wellbeing, which affects their work behaviours. The result corroborates Tyokusu, Emakwu and Ejoha

(2019)'s study that principals' objective implementation of procedural justice matters more to staff than any reward they can get from the school. This means that vice principals' negative work behaviours in Anambra State will change when principals implement procedural justice with objectivity.

Conclusion

This study concluded that principals' interpersonal relationship and organizational justice are significant predictors of vice principals' work behaviours. When principals effectively adopt respect for diversity as one of the dimensions of their interpersonal relationship, they create a conducive school environment where vice principals (and other school members) feel connected and committed to the achievement of educational goals which is shown in their work behaviours. Similarly, when principals positively adopt or incorporate procedural justice as part of their organizational justice behaviours in their relationship with vice principals, they create a school atmosphere which enhances vice principals' organizational performance and organizational citizenship behaviours and reduces or even eliminates absenteeism and turnover.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made, based on the findings:

1. Anambra State secondary school principals' should have a very high regard for vice principals and see them as very important and indispensable partners in their relationships with them.
2. Anambra State secondary school principals should elevate the image of their vice principals to students, parents and other school members.
3. Vice principals and other school members in Anambra State public secondary schools should also respect, value and empathize with the principals.
4. Principals in secondary schools should be impartial in their relationship and organizational justice with vice principals and other school members.

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